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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

After almost two decades of operations, Gemini is now well-established as Canada's forefront optical/near-infrared observing facility. In this paper we review the use of Gemini by the Canadian community over the past decade. The Canadian community has been well-served by Gemini, and this is demonstrated using metrics such as publication statistics, press releases, theses using Gemini data, the exploitation of instrumentation development opportunities, and student training opportunities. We describe the vital role that Gemini will continue to play into the future. Over the next 5 years Gemini will enjoy an instrumental renaissance, with the commissioning of a revitalized instrumentation suite that is very well-aligned with the general needs of the Canadian astronomical community into the 2020s and beyond. These instruments include GHOST, SCORPIO, IGRINS2, an upgraded GPI, GIRMOS and a new GN-AO system. The Gemini International Agreement will end circa 2027, and we argue that it is crucial to remain in the Gemini partnership past 2027 into the extremely large optical telescopes era. In particular, Gemini will (1) be an important testbed for future instrument developments, (2) offer capabilities not offered by 30 meter-class telescopes until well into the 2030s (such as high-resolution spectroscopy in the Northern hemisphere), and (3) continue to offer access to both hemispheres, providing pathfinder science that will enable programs on 30 meter-class facilities.

Lead author and affiliation	Stéphanie Côté (NRC Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics)
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Email address of lead author	Stephanie.Cote@nrc-cnrc.gc.ca
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Other authors and affiliations

Tim Davidge, Joel Roediger, Eric Steinbring and Laura Ferrarese (NRC Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics)

John Blakeslee (Gemini Observatory, La Serena, Chile)

Sarah Gallagher (Western University, London)

Craig Heinke (University of Alberta)

Laura Parker (McMster University)

Suresh Sivanandam (Dept of Astronomy & Astrophysics, Dunlap Institute for Astronomy & Astrophysics, University of Toronto)

Kim Venn (University of Victoria)

1 Introduction

The twin 8m Gemini North and South telescopes, situated on Maunakea, HI, and Cerro Pachon, Chile, have been part of the Canadian astronomical landscape for almost 20 years. Gemini is Canada's forefront optical/near-infrared facility and has had a major impact on our community. The Gemini Telescopes hold distinct benefits when compared to the other 8-10m-class facilities worldwide:

- They are inherently competitive, optimized to deliver good image quality at sites that enjoy good natural seeing conditions;
- With sites in both hemispheres Gemini is the only ground-based observatory in its class capable of offering full sky coverage;
- The Gemini observing model allows for very flexible scheduling, enabling it to excel in particular for time-critical follow-up and target-of-opportunities observations;
- With its new Strategic Scientific Plan (Blakeslee et al 2019) and a recent major investment from the NSF, which will allow significant upgrades to both telescopes, Gemini is guaranteed to play a vital role into the future.

The current Gemini International Agreement will expire in 2021. The November 2018 Board meeting was the Assessment Point for the partnership, when all partners had to declare their intentions to renew their share in the Gemini partnership past 2021 and agree to sign on to a new Agreement to be valid from 2021 until about 2027. In early 2018, an independent Canadian Gemini Assessment Point Panel was appointed by NRC to make a recommendation about Canada's position. The Panel reviewed extensive material about Gemini contributions in Canada, including an open community survey and a Townhall discussion. The Panel recommended that Canada remain in the Gemini partnership at the same level. At the November 2018 Board meeting, the other partners have also reiterated their commitment to remain in the partnership and at the same level.

In this White Paper we will address the following: how Gemini will meet our future expectations and continue to play an important role in the Canadian astronomy landscape at the end of the 2020s. Section 2 will demonstrate how the Canadian community has been well-served by Gemini over the last decade. Section 3 provides information on the present state of instrument development and operations, while Section 4 presents near-future plans. Finally, Section 5 addresses the future role of Gemini at the end of the coming decade into the era of extremely large telescopes.

2 Review of Canadian use of Gemini over the last decade

Canada's share in the partnership is $\sim 18.15\%$, and statistics indicate that Gemini has served the Canadian community extremely well in the last decade. A review of publications covering 2009 to 2015 indicates that Canadians are authors (first or co-authors) on 20.4% of all Gemini peer-reviewed publications (257 Canadian papers out of 1258 total Gemini papers). This compares well with our effective share of observing time of 14.7% over that period (before the UK withdrawal in 2012 Canada had a 15% share in Gemini; and 10% of the observing time goes to the non-paying hosts Hawaii and Chile). Of the 257 Canadian papers, 45% used Gemini-North data, 37% Gemini-South, and 18% use data from both Gemini-North and -South. With regards to instrumentation, the twin GMOS units have clearly dominated our Gemini paper count, accounting for almost 60% of all the Canadian papers. The other instruments, all from the IR suite, share equitably the rest of the papers, with the exception of Flamingos-2 and GSAOI+GeMs which contribute less than 2% of the paper count (but note that these have only been available in the queue since 2013A and 2013B respectively). What is most remarkable is the science impact of these Canadian papers. The paper impact is calculated as the ratio of its raw citation count to the median of the raw citation distribution for all of the papers published in the *Astronomical Journal* from the same year (kindly provided by D. Crabtree). The Canadian Gemini papers have an amazing impact of 4.38, much above the overall Gemini papers average impact of 3.1. Canadian papers based on Gemini-South data have been more impactful at 5.0 compared

to the North (4.2), and this is primarily due to the very high impact of GPI papers in particular (7.0). The Canadian Gemini papers thus have had a larger impact than papers from the other three most influential ground-based telescopes from this period 2011 – 15 (ALMA, Keck, VISTA), with mean impact factors in the range 4.10-4.20. Amongst the top 10 highly-cited Gemini papers of that period, half of them include a Canadian author (first or co-author). These papers deal with topics as diverse as supernovae, quasars at high-redshift, and gamma-ray bursts.

Figure 1: Impact of Canadian Gemini papers, split by site, compared to those of the whole Gemini partnership. On average, every year the Canadian papers have more impact than the overall Gemini ones. The South papers have had higher impact in the recent years thanks to GPI exoplanet papers.

Roughly 40% of all Canadian proposals include an MSc or PhD student as a PI or co-I. The percentage of students who are PIs on proposals is the highest in Canada compared to all other Gemini partners and is a wonderful training opportunity for them to take on a leadership role in proposal writing. The Canadian share of Gemini time enables Canadian supervisors and their students to start ambitious programs on Gemini with a reasonable expectation that time might be allocated and at least some data obtained, sometimes over several semesters. Gemini has thus proven to be a powerful thesis-producing machine for Canada: there are now 63 MSc and PhD theses using Gemini data, and 9 more that are ongoing! In recent years there has been an average of 5 Canadian theses produced per year using Gemini data. Thus during its 19 year lifetime Gemini has enabled more theses than any other major facility to which Canadian astronomers have had access. The theses were completed at 14 Canadian universities. The most prolific are University of Victoria (19), Université de Montréal (12) and University of Toronto (10). Note that this list is incomplete due to inconsistencies in the way that thesis information is catalogued, and so this ranking might reflect some biases. For example, the CGO is more likely to notice the theses carried out in Victoria (with many students supervised by NRC astronomers). Alternatively, it might also be that staff and students in Victoria are simply more aware of Gemini capabilities in general because of the CGO’s local presence.

Canadian undergraduate students have also benefited from our Gemini partnership, through paid internship positions (each lasting approx. four months). During the period 2009 – 2017, Canadian undergraduates enrolled in co-op programs have filled 33 internship positions with Gemini. These students have served in multiple capacities at Gemini, not only as science interns but also as operations interns or science software testers.

Many more Canadian students, a total of 31 from 2009 to 2017, have had the chance to visit the Gemini telescopes, either through the “Maunakea Graduate School (MKGS)” or through the Gemini “Bring One, Get One!” (BOGO) program. The MKGS program was created and managed by Prof. Stéphane Courteau (Queen’s), and is sponsored by Queen’s University, the Dunlap Institute, the Institute for Research on Exoplanets, in addition to CFHT and Gemini. It provides promising Canadian graduate students with educational and training opportunities in observational astronomy, and the chance to acquire important skills beyond their university curricula. The MKGS includes extended visits at the CFHT headquarters and Gemini-North facility in Waimea and Hilo, where students attend lectures by astronomers and engineers, and shadow astronomers during evening operations. The lectures cover astronomical instrumentation, observatory operations, astronomical methods, data acquisition, data archiving and management, data reduction, public outreach, the Hawaiian culture, and more. Students also com-

pete for guaranteed Director’s Discretionary Time (DDT) to run their own program on CFHT and Gemini. These DDT projects are then carried through observation planning, data acquisition, reduction, analysis, and, ideally, publication. The BOGO program was launched in 2014B by Gemini, to encourage students from across the partnership to experience observing with the telescopes. It subsidizes the cost of their travel to join a senior astronomer on an observing run. The program was designed to have a wide scope of application, accepting students under multiple observing modes (classical, queue, and large programs priority visiting). Another program for students is the NSERC CREATE training program on ‘New Technologies for Canadian Observatories’ initiated in 2017, and including the Gemini Observatory as one of the founding partners. Led by Kim Venn (U of Victoria) and including researchers from eight Canadian universities, government labs, observatories, and over a dozen Canadian industries, this program offer internships in industry and observatory partners with unique, hands-on experience in astronomical instrumentation technologies, integrated software developments, and operations. So far two top PhD students have completed internships at Gemini, working on a new python-based GNIRS data reduction pipeline.

Canadians have also been very prolific with press releases: from 2009 to 2017 Canadians have been authors or co-authors on 46% of all Gemini science press releases. Canadians were the lead authors for 14% of these, in line with our effective observing time share of 14.7%. Canadian press releases cover a wide range of topics, although exoplanets are clearly dominating the output. The most prolific Gemini instrument for Canadian press release is GMOS (with 38% of announcements), which is not surprising considering that the majority of the requested Canadian time is for GMOS.

Canada has also benefited from strong involvement in instrumentation development for Gemini. We have been a major player in developing a large number of new instruments and facilities over the years, and some of the most successful Gemini instruments have had a Canadian stamp. These include the GMOS spectrographs, the ALTAIR AO facility, the Flamingos-2 OIWFS, the Gemini Planet Imager, the Gemini Remote access to CFHT/Espadons (GRACES), and the high-resolution optical spectrograph GHOST (currently in development). The contracts and subcontracts obtained from Gemini funds over the last decades have benefited two dozen institutes and companies all across all Canada. From our GAP study, we found that over the last 5 years (2012 to 2017) Canada had received over 30% of all the Gemini Instrument Development Funds allocations. But beyond the sheer dollar value of development contracts, one must appreciate the intellectual enrichment it has brought to the Canadian teams of engineers and astronomers designing and building them, all to their benefit. Thanks to the increased detailed technical knowledge of these instruments, Canadians have had an advantage in using them more efficiently, to the point of getting large shares of observing time (e.g. the GPI team who won the GPIES campaign time of 890 hours). Furthermore, this effort, knowledge and know-how have also been invaluable to benefit the development of facilities for the next-generation of telescopes (e.g. NFIRAOS for the TMT).

3 Gemini Now

Gemini has a broad Canadian user base, with more Canadian users than any other major facility. Not surprisingly the demand by Canadians for Gemini time thus remains healthy, with oversubscription rates for PI time of approximately 2.4 (e.g. higher than CFHT), with rates between 4 to 6 for Band 1 (which is the highest priority time that PIs are aiming for) over the last 10 years. Canadians are predominantly interested in the optical instruments with both GMOS-N and GMOS-S securing the highest proportion of requested time, although the community’s interest has always been very broad with every facility instrument being requested on a regular basis. Figure 2 shows the percentage of time requested from each instrument, averaged over the last 3 years (semesters 2017A to 2019B).

The most requested instruments on both telescopes are GMOS-N and GMOS-S (optical imagers and spectrographs), with over 40% of the time requested in each hemisphere. This is followed by GNIRS in the North, and Flamingos-2 in the South (both near-infrared spectrographs). The pie charts show that the demand is there in the Canadian community for every single facility instrument. The Canadian optical/infrared community, despite its modest size compared to the US, is thus very diverse in its needs.

The Canadian community has also had access to time on Subaru through the Gemini-Subaru time exchange program. Over the last 5 years very few proposals were received from Canadians for Subaru, with an average of

Figure 2: Time requested on each instrument at Gemini-North (left) and South (right) averaged over 6 semesters (2017A to 2019B). GMOS-N and GMOS-S dominate the demand, with over 40% of the time requested by Canadians on each telescope. Note that two visitor instruments, IGRINS and GASP, were only offered for one semester during the period covered here, and received over 44% and 18% resp. of the total time requested in the semester they were offered. Overall the demand is very diversified and well spread over all the facility instruments offered.

1.4 per semester. The interests of Canadians for Subaru instruments is varied with no one single instrument being more popular than the others. See Michael Balogh's white paper on Subaru for more information.

There are also two proposal modes that have been implemented in the last few years that greatly improve efficiency and flexibility of Gemini observations: Fast Turnaround and Gemini Large and Long Programs.

The Fast Turnaround Program (FTP) offers roughly 10% of the time on each telescope to a monthly proposal submission and assessment, with data obtained for accepted proposals 1-4 months after the end-of-month submission deadline. A novel aspect of the FTP is that the proposals are peer-reviewed by those who apply for this time on any given month. The CGO originally led the effort to develop the necessary software to support the FTP process, and it has been successfully running now on both telescopes for several years, gaining momentum in Canada, where the demand is increasing, with a total of 21 proposals submitted this year so far, amounting to as much as 39% of the total awarded time from the Program.

Large and Long Programs (LLP) are programs that require significantly more time than a partner typically approves for a single program and/or extend over two to six semesters. This was something that Canadian users had been wanting to see on Gemini for a long time, and it was finally offered starting in 2014A, on an annual basis. Each participating partner allocates 20% of its time to a common LLP pool, and proposals are reviewed by a single international TAC. Although only a small number of Canadian PIs have been awarded time for LLPs so far, some of their programs are amongst the largest ever accepted on Gemini so the share of allocated time exceeds the 20% share of time that Canada had to allocate to participate. Over semesters 2014B – 2020A (note that time for LLPs is allocated in advance because the programs can extend over several semesters), Canadian PIs have been awarded 23% of the available LLP time. Moreover from 2014B – 2017A the Canadian-led LLPs have been highly successful in terms of observing time, with 512.5 hours (or 38% of available LLP time) actually being executed. Canadian-led LLPs have thus had a higher execution rate than LLPs from other partners. Moreover, these numbers do not take into account the many dozens of Canadians co-Is on many US-led LLPs. In summary, the LLP program has been very beneficial to Canadians, allowing them to lead or participate in substantial science programs. For example:

- GOGREEN, led by Michael Balogh, is the largest LLP program ever allocated time on Gemini (530 hours over 10 semesters on both telescopes for deep spectroscopy) and was completed in July 2019. It aims to answer critical questions about galaxy formation through a controlled study of galaxies at $1 < z < 1.5$ as a function of stellar mass, halo mass and redshift. The first published science paper (Chan et al. 2019) based on an early subset of the sample, provides exquisite measurements of the H-band luminosity function, and demonstrates that environmental quenching of star formation is in place at $z > 1$, leading to a gradual build up of faint, quiescent galaxies in dense environments. Work in preparation shows that the fraction of

quenched galaxies, the shape of the stellar mass function, the halo mass dependence, the ages of quiescent galaxies (Webb et al. in prep) and the distribution of star formation rates (Old et al. in prep) do not appear to be consistent with any of the current models or expectations based on lower redshift data, thus ushering in a new paradigm to explain how galaxies evolve in dense environments.

- Another approved project (2018) is the 150h program on the chemistry of metal-poor stars. Lead by Kim Venn (UofVictoria), the survey will acquire GRACES high-resolution spectroscopy on ~ 80 extremely metal-poor stars found in the Pristine survey (Starkenburger et al 2017). Accurate chemical abundances for important elements will help explore the variety of nucleosynthetic pathways in metal-poor stars, core-collapse supernovae and the first stars.

Note that since 2018 Canadians have also been invited to submit Subaru Intensive proposals (their equivalent of the Gemini LLPs) through the Gemini-Subaru Exchange program; however no Canadian yet has taken on this opportunity.

In the last few years, Gemini has also improved responsiveness and connection to its users via new initiatives, such as the creation of a User's Committee and the establishment of Priority Visitor Observing (PVO) mode to encourage PIs to come observe at the base facilities. The User's committee provides feedback on all areas of operations that affect current users. This committee has already been effective at getting the observatory to prioritize issues that are considered most critical by users such as the production of data reduction pipelines: the new Python data reduction pipeline DRAGONS is expected to be launched this coming year. As for the PVO, it encourages PIs to observe on-site, by scheduling a block of time for them that exceeds their program allocation. The PIs are then free to observe their program or to skip it depending on the observing conditions. After their run, the unexecuted time remaining in the program is placed back in the regular queue. PVO is the default observing mode for LLPs, but is also offered to Band 1 standard queue programs. This ensures that Canadian users can have a direct observing experience at Gemini if they so wish.

4 Gemini in the near-future

In the coming decade Gemini will continue to be Canada's forefront optical/infrared ground-based facility, until the first TMT instruments start to be commissioned (circa 2030). Gemini is completely renewing its instrument suite in the years to come, with the procurement of a slew of new cutting-edge instruments. Moreover these new instruments are superbly aligned with Canadian interests. The large NSF grant awarded to Gemini last year (26MUS\$) will mostly be spent on the development of an advanced queue-operated multi-conjugate AO system for Gemini-North, which is a capability that the Canadian community has been requesting for many years. Over the next 5 years the instrumental renaissance on Gemini will consist of:

- GHOST, the Gemini High resolution Optical SpecTrograph, will deliver two-object plus sky spectroscopy over a 7.5 arcmin field of view, with full simultaneous wavelength coverage from the ultraviolet to the silicon cutoff (363 to 1000 nm) at resolutions $R=50K$. There is also a single-object mode with resolution $R=75K$. It will be capable of a radial velocity precision of 10 m/s over 430 to 750 nm. It also spatially samples each target over a field of 1.2 arcsec. It will be a workhorse spectrograph ideally suited for stellar chemical abundances studies, precision radial velocities, and quick follow-up of ToO transient objects. High throughput is one of its strict science requirements, such that it will exceed that of any comparable instrument on any other 8m class telescope. Its science niche will thus be the ability to study faint sources on the borderline of feasibility with other spectrographs. This is important as such a capability will likely not be available on a 30m class facility until at least the end of the 2020s. Thus, GHOST will be a forefront instrument for some time to come. It is being built by AAO, ANU and NRC-Herzberg and nearing completion, with delivery to G-South scheduled for later this year and commissioning in the spring of 2020.
- SCORPIO, the Spectrograph and Camera for Observations of Rapid Phenomena in the Infrared and Optical, is an 8-channel imager and spectrograph that will simultaneously observe the g, r, i, z, Y, J, H, and Ks

bands in a square field-of-view of $3' \times 3'$, or a circular one with a diameter of $4.24'$. It will also obtain long slit ($3'$) spectroscopy with a resolution of $R = 4,000$, simultaneously covering the range between 0.37 - 2.35 microns. The eight independent arms in SCORPIO allow the user to adjust exposure times in each bandpass for increased efficiency and the best match to observing conditions. By using state-of-the-art detectors it will have negligible readout times enabling high time resolution observations, thus opening up a new parameter-space for Gemini users for the study of fast-changing phenomena. With wideband spectral cover (optical and IR) it will support LSST follow-up targets but also a wide range of static-sky science such as primitive solar system bodies, stellar explosions, accreting compact objects and high-redshift sources. All detectors have now been received (4 E2V CCDs, 4 H2RG IR arrays) and the team led by M. Robberto (STSci) and SwRI have passed their CDR. Commissioning is expected for Spring 2022.

- IGRINS2 is part of Korea's contribution to joining the Gemini partnership, and is based on the popular IGRINS that is visiting Gemini-South for 2020A. It is a high-resolution ($R=45K$) near-infrared echelle spectrometer. It can observe the entire H and K windows, from 1.45 to 2.5 microns, in a single exposure. When it was offered in 2018A it was the most requested instrument by the Canadian community on Gemini-South. It is suited for studies of the dense interstellar medium, star formation, and the early evolution of stars and planetary systems.
- GIRMOS is a multi-object IR spectrograph being designed and built by a Canadian consortium led by Suresh Sivanandam (UofT) and including eight Canadian universities and NRC, with funding provided by a CFI grant with additional funds from provincial partners. Unlike others, GIRMOS is a visitor instrument, and is a pathfinder and a model for future development work at Canadian universities. It is being designed to tackle a broad range of science drivers, including studies of star clusters in the MW, the stellar contents of nearby galaxies, and galaxies at high redshift. It is thus a workhorse instrument that will see significant use. GIRMOS is unique as it uses four IFUs that will be deployed over a 2 arcmin field of view to obtain spectra with an angular resolution near the telescope diffraction limit of objects in the wavelength range $1 - 2.4\mu\text{m}$. Wavefront distortion is corrected by a combination of the Gemini MCAO system (GeMS) and a custom MOAO system. GIRMOS passed its CoDR in mid-September of this year, and is now preparing for PDR. There is the likely prospect of future work, as a GIRMOS-like capability ('TIRMOS') is actively being considered as a capability for the TMT.
- GNAO is a sophisticated multi-conjugate AO system for G-North, made possible thanks to NSF funding. The aging ALTAIR AO system is single-conjugate and does not fully exploit Maunakea's site, which is the best in the world for AO performance. Furthermore, no MCAO system such as GeMS exists in the northern hemisphere and there are no plans for one, until TMT's NFIRAOS around 2030. The GN-MCAO system is planned to be much more than a simple copy of GeMS. Its baseline requirements call for a two-arcminute field of view with a 30% Strehl correction in the K band under median seeing, with a goal of achieving 50% Strehl; PSF astrometry better than 1 mas, and it must be easily operable so it can be scheduled nightly in the queue. To get an even larger corrected field-of-view with broad wavelength coverage, six LGSs coupled with the deployment of an adaptive deformable secondary mirror will enable GLAO correction for improved imaging and spectroscopic performance that can be fed to all instruments over the full wavelength range of the telescope. Finally, a new modern IR imager capable of taking full advantage of the GN-MCAO system will be needed. GN-MCAO and a GNAO Imager will enable detailed stellar populations studies, supernova physics, proper motions, and galactic archaeology; also enabled are detailed studies on sub-kiloparsec scales in the rest-frame optical of galaxy morphology and interactions at $z \sim 2$, the peak of star formation activity and galaxy assembly; and high-resolution narrow-band imaging of Lyman-alpha emitters at redshifts $z > 7$. This GN-MCAO system will be perfectly complementary to JWST: because of JWST's L2 orbit and constraints on pointing angles, most of its targets will be accessible only for limited periods each year. GN-MCAO, with a similar spatial resolution and field-of-view as NIRCAM on JWST, will be the only facility capable of monitoring high-priority targets (which will be especially important for time-domain astronomy). It will also allow for simultaneous AO and spectroscopic follow-up of LSST targets visible from the North. This

will continue the legacy of AO leadership established by Gemini. Gemini is now producing more AO-based papers than any other telescope.

- The NSF grant will also enable development of world-leading time-domain infrastructure. Gemini will become THE premier facility for follow-up spectroscopic and rapid imaging investigations of targets identified by LSST, by exploiting its two-hemisphere access advantage, its nimble operational modes, and its instruments especially suited for such studies (particularly SCORPIO). Gemini is in the process of enabling automatic triggering from a filtered stream of transient alerts for PI-led proposals. The AEON network of telescopes (Gemini, LCO and SOAR, so far) will distribute requests to telescopes (as appropriate, depending on magnitude, declination, etc) to follow up a particular trigger. Gemini is improving its observatory control system and data reduction pipelines to enable efficient ToO observations and rapid data analysis. These improvements will place Gemini at the forefront of fast-moving science such as gravitational-wave and high-energy neutrino follow-up, supernovae, gamma-ray bursts, X-ray binaries, lower-luminosity rare transients, and rapidly-moving objects (e.g. ‘Oumuamua), and support the continued development of Canadian multi-messenger astronomy. At the same time Gemini is committed to make sure that the transient follow-up strategy at Gemini-South does not harm “static-sky science”, thereby satisfying the interests of the majority of the community members. In Canada the interest for TDA is rather modest at present, and so far ToO proposals constitute only around 15% of all received proposals. But because of the entanglement of the Canadian and American astronomical communities (with students, postdocs, university hires moving in and out on each side) it is to be expected that the LSST impact will be significant in Canada, especially if we gain some official participation in the project as enabled by the new in-kind contributions opportunities (see Wes Fraser White Paper on LSST).

5 Gemini beyond the Current Agreement

The current Gemini International Agreement is due to end in 2021 and a new International Gemini Agreement is being prepared which will likely span the period from 2021-2027. At that point, partners will go through another Gemini Assessment Point to state their intent to remain in the Gemini partnership post 2027. Thus a key issue to consider by the Canadian community in the context of the LRP is the future of Gemini beyond 2027.

The 2027 date is significant as it is only a few years after the commissioning of the new GNAO system in the North and of GIRMOS (both due by end of 2024). These are new capabilities with much interest in the Canadian community. It thus may not be wise to decide to diminish our share of Gemini time (or pull out entirely) when so much exciting science would be in the making thanks to these new world-unique instruments.

Gemini-South will offer the only access to the south for the Canadian community, which is important for maximizing the science impact of ALMA and SKA, both located in the southern hemisphere.

Canadian time on the TMT and other facilities (eg: JWST) will be modest, and if our share in TMT is, after NSF entry in the project, at the level of 10% or less, then Gemini will still be needed to accommodate our community needs. When a share of time on a facility is too small then there is the danger that it will only cater to a small group of astronomers. Gemini can continue to enable a large number of students theses. And instruments like GIRMOS and GHOST will continue to offer Canadian astronomers unique capabilities well into the 30-meter era. As for the JWST, its nominal lifetime is 5.5 years up to 10 years max (to be decommissioned by around 2030).

Access to Gemini will also give Canadians an advantage to test instrument prototypes for TMT instruments and other technological concepts. This will be even more true if Gemini adopts as its new RTC the modular concept developed for TMT by HAA (a possibility that is being discussed). Like the TMT, the Gemini telescopes were designed for high angular resolution imaging, and so they will become important testbeds for TMT instrument development, which is of importance considering the enormous amount of resources needed for developing a TMT-sized instrument (in the range of 40 to 50M\$ each).

It should also be emphasized that the first generation of TMT instruments will in no way cover the wide range of capabilities offered on Gemini. In particular high-resolution spectroscopy at spectral resolution > 8000 in the optical and > 4000 in the near-infrared will not be available on the TMT until its 2nd generation of instruments

well into the 2030s nor on the JWST. The recent popularity of the visitor instrument IGRINS on Gemini-South, which when it was first offered in semester 2018A received more Canadian proposals than any other instrument including GMOS-S, shows that there is a strong appetite in Canada for high-resolution spectroscopy.

The transient science enabled by the LSST will still be in its infancy in 2027. While TMT might be able to follow-up on fainter, more distant triggers, Gemini time will still be needed to follow-up and characterize local triggers. Because it will still be a young science, there will still be a big need to understand properly all the local brighter objects, an understanding of which is critical for interpreting more distant objects. An efficient system might develop where Gemini would follow-up at the start of the trigger and if deemed to be an interesting object then as it dims, TMT would pick it up to study the rest of its light curve. This is just one area of science amongst many where TMT and Gemini will work hand-in-hand.

In summary, Canadian access to Gemini will remain crucial even in the TMT era. We therefore urge the LRP panel to recommend that Canada renew its participation in the Gemini partnership past the coming Agreement ending around 2027. If this is done then Canadians can continue to benefit successfully from the many opportunities offered by Gemini.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Gemini is completely renewing its instrument suite in the coming five years, utilizing its Instrument Development Fund, and also thanks to the NSF award. These new instruments will have world-leading capabilities. As described in Section 4, Gemini will be transformed into an unprecedented efficient LSST-trigger follow-up machine thereby leading the scientific discoveries in the emergent field of time-domain astronomy. Not only will it have an infrastructure optimized for fast follow-up of transients but it will also be equipped with an optimal spectrograph to do so, SCORPIO (described above), which will also enable high time resolution observations thus opening up a new parameter space of discoveries. Meanwhile on the North the unique GN-MCAO will transform the fields of stellar population studies and galactic archaeology. GIRMOS will be a completely novel instrument, that is also a pathfinder for multi-object IFU observations on the TMT. This is a Canadian effort that is transforming the model for future Canadian university-based instrumentation efforts. Through its high- z integral field spectroscopy, it will have deep impact on our understanding of dynamics, metallicity, stellar populations and star formation rates of galaxies at $1 < z < 3$.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

As the Gemini telescopes are extant facilities, the major risk areas are related to the development of new capabilities, rather than the structures themselves. For Gemini South, there is a risk associated with placing an emphasis on time domain science, as this is a new field. Still, the instruments have workhorse capabilities that will allow them to do forefront science that is not related to the time domain. We emphasize that the emphasis on the time domain has the potential of reaping a transformational science return. Even if no new astronomical phenomena are discovered, this still allows better characterizing of the events already known such as gravitational-wave and high-energy neutrino follow-up, supernovae, gamma-ray bursts, X-ray binaries, and rapidly moving objects such as interstellar objects (e.g. ‘Oumuamua). For Gemini-North, there is a modest risk that Subaru or Keck may decide to build a competing sophisticated AO system in the North. Neither is currently executing a GLAO design. And even if those were budgeted now, they would be behind schedule compared to GN-MCAO.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Absolutely. Our share of Gemini time is large enough to allow dozens of Canadian PIs every semester to lead

their programs on either telescope. The Large and Long program has already allowed several Canadian-led teams to pursue substantial science programs over the last few years. The remarkable impact of Canadian Gemini papers and numerous press releases demonstrate how this Canadian leadership has been very fruitful. Furthermore, NRC and Canadian universities (typically in partnership) have led Gemini instrument developments for a majority of the current instrument suite, which is outstanding considering our modest share of < 20%. And GIRMOS – which recently passed its CoDR – has pioneered a path for future university-led instrumentation projects. We are also expected to have considerable strategic leadership since we have two members on each of the Gemini Board and STAC (in addition to having our turn to chair both of these), in addition to numerous representatives on the Users Committee, the Operations Working Group and others such as the TDA or AO working group, as well as the AURA Oversight Committee. Canada is the second largest partner in Gemini and hence has an important voice in all matters.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Yes. Gemini is the facility with the largest user pool in the Canadian community and, as discussed above, it has already generated more Canadian theses than any other telescope that Canadians have access to. Many in the Canadian community are actively involved in instrumentation projects for Gemini. The best example is GIRMOS, entirely funded by a CFI grant led by a Canadian University astronomer (Suresh Sivanandam, U of Toronto) and involving 9 Canadian institutes and over 20 Canadian astronomers. Another Canadian group interested in exoplanets is actively working on a GPI upgrade for enhanced sensitivity and a move to Gemini-North and financing has just been secured. As for involvement of the Canadian community in the decision making: the community-at-large is often polled (by the CGO, the STAC or User's Committee members) about various issues, so that Canadian positions can be relayed to Gemini via all the respective committees and channels. Distinct from other partners, a Canadian Gemini Science Committee, composed of 6-8 astronomy university professors throughout the community, help our STAC representatives through discussion to form their positions on important points on the agenda ahead of the STAC meeting.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

The opportunities for the Canadian community over the next decade will be tremendous thanks to the new transformational instruments that will be commissioned in the coming years (as discussed above). With the recent commitment to renew the Gemini Agreement until about 2027 this means Canadians will be able to continue enjoying all the benefits that come from our Gemini partnership. This also includes more opportunities to participate in future instrument procurements. Indeed at the time of writing the Request for proposal for a new Gemini-North Imager has just been released and several Canadian groups have expressed interest to participate. Beyond 2027 the LRP panel must recommend that Canada stays in the Gemini partnership so that Canadians can continue to enjoy all future opportunities through 2030 and beyond. All of the experience and know-how developed in the Canadian community with each of the numerous contracts over the last two decades bolsters our position to bid for new contracts to come over the next decade and beyond.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Gemini has the best cost-benefit ratio of any 8-m class observatory. Keck has been offering nights to other nations (such as Australia) and the cost per night is actually close to the cost of a night on Gemini; however only a very limited number of nights are offered and this comes with no voice in the telescope governance. For

Subaru, a delegation of Canadian astronomers as well as Gemini staff who took part in the Subaru partnership meeting in early 2018 reported that the cost per night for a new partner in Subaru would be almost 4 times the cost of a Gemini night (3 times if opting out of archive access), due in part to their much higher operating costs (twice that of Gemini). For ESO, the comparison is more difficult because by becoming an ESO member one would get access to much more than 8m-class telescopes but also a collection of smaller facilities. The entry price into the ESO partnership would therefore be huge, and this is in addition to the annual membership costs (from discussions at the last LRP these were larger than our annual Gemini contributions). The only other 8-meter class telescope for which Canadians might get time for a lower cost is the LSST, since they are now accepting in-kind contributions, and if Canada and LSST identify and agree to enough of these it could secure an interesting chunk of time on the telescope. However this is an imaging-only survey telescope, and hence, as a replacement for a multi-instrument telescope such as Gemini, would not satisfy the whole optical/infrared Canadian community, which as we have shown above in section 3, is very diverse in its needs (see Figure 2).

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

At the November 2018 "Gemini Assessment Point" Board meeting, all partners reiterated their decision to stay in the Gemini partnership past 2021 and enter into a new Agreement to last until about 2027, at their current share of telescope time. Thus the Gemini partnership is now very stable at least until the expiry of the next Agreement. With the recent large grant from the NSF, Gemini has been able to launch full-steam into realizing its Scientific Vision for the coming decade. Key instruments are already fully-funded, for example GIRMOS through a CFI grant combined with university funding and provincial grants. Hence, budgetary concerns are not expected to be an obstacle to realizing the scientific goals of the coming decade. A potential programmatic concern for Canada is about the governance plan, with the imminent start of NCOA in the US putting Gemini, LSST and NOAO all under one umbrella led by NCOA. If this turns out to be sub-optimal for Gemini or Canada, the way to mitigate this would be for Canada and other small partners to advocate for change at the Board level and if necessary to vote not to renew AURA's five-year contract to be the managing organization of Gemini and choose one of the many other organizations that competed for the contract last time.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Definitely, for each of the above. Gemini, with its broad array of facility and visitor instruments, offers a huge suite of flexible capabilities of interest to Canadian astronomers from every field of study - including interdisciplinary ones, such as gravitational waves, high-energy physics, etc. The industry opportunities are numerous, as described above, and Canada has been extremely successful in the past at seizing these opportunities, with two dozen of Canadian institutes and companies benefiting from procurement over the last decades. Gemini has also provided many opportunities for HQP training as presented in Section 2 with 33 Canadian student internships in the last decade, and as many other students visiting for an observing run, and a record number of Canadian MSc and PhD theses produced over the years. Gemini has been a pioneer for positive change in Canada with respect to EDI, for example by being the first Canadian facility to modify its proposal format so that the gender of the PI is not disclosed to the TAC (all investigators are listed in alphabetical order), to mitigate unconscious biases. Gemini has provided excellent support for outreach in Canada, as is demonstrated by the numerous Canadian Gemini press releases (see Section 2), so much that Canadians have participated in almost half of all Gemini science press releases over the last decade.

References

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